

Synthesis and crystal structure of *cis*-dioxomolybdenum(VI) complex with salicylaldehyde-2-pyrazinoylhydrazone

G. S. Sanyal^{a*}, R. Ganguly^a, P. K. Nath^a and R. J. Butcher^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani-741 235, India

E-mail : rakesh_ganguly@yahoo.com Fax : 91-33-5828282

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Howard University, Washington, D.C. 20059, U.S.A.

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$\text{MoO}_2\text{Cl}_2(\text{DMF})_2$ reacts with salicylaldehyde-2-pyrazinoylhydrazone (SAPH) in methanol to afford the title complex. X-Ray structure analysis reveals that the complex possesses the usual *cis*- MoO_2^{2+} moiety and SAPH behaves as a dianionic tridentate donor coordinating through azomethine nitrogen, enolic and phenolic oxygens. The sixth coordination site around Mo is occupied by a water molecule in the distorted octahedral geometry of the complex. The second water molecule is present as water of crystallization.

Recent years have aroused considerable interest in the coordination chemistry of molybdenum being the only second row transition element important to the living world as essential micronutrient¹ in microorganism, plants and animals. Certain molybdoenzymes have oxidized form of the *cis*-dioxomolybdenum cation, $[\text{MoO}_2]^{2+}$ as the cofactor. In addition to this, molybdenum chemistry in catalytic and material science has catapulted the search for new structures in which $[\text{MoO}_2]^{2+}$ moiety is coordinated to ligands containing nitrogen, oxygen and/or sulfur donors. In the last couple of decades, a number of molybdenum(VI) complexes with Schiff base has been reported and majority of these contain the *cis*- $[\text{MoO}_2]^{2+}$ moiety which has been proposed as models for the active sites of oxo-transfer molybdoenzymes².

In the present paper, we describe the synthesis and characterization of a new complex of *cis*-dioxomolybdenum(VI) with salicylaldehyde-2-pyrazinoylhydrazone (SAPH). An X-ray diffraction analysis has been performed on the title complex.

Results and Discussion

The crystal data are given in Table 1 and the selected bond distances and bond angles are listed in Table 2. The final atomic coordinates and other crystal data, have been deposited as supplementary material with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC-147148), from whom copies are available on request. The view of the molecular structure of the complex and its atomic numbering is shown in Fig. 1. The X-ray analysis indicates distorted octahedral environment about molybdenum(VI), the SAPH ligand serving as doubly negative tridentate ligand in the

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement for the complex

Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{MoN}_4\text{O}_6$	
Formula weight	404.20	
Temp.	293(2) K	
Wavelength	0.71073 Å	
Crystal system	Monoclinic	
Space group	$P2(1)/n$	
Unit cell dimensions	$a = 12.140(2)$ Å	$\alpha = 90^\circ$
	$b = 10.3095(6)$ Å	$\beta = 111.365(11)^\circ$
	$c = 12.2818(17)$ Å	$\gamma = 90^\circ$
Volume	$1431.5(3)$ Å ³	
Z	4	
Density (calcd.)	1.875 mg/m ³	
Absorption coefficient	0.955 mm ⁻¹	
$F(000)$	808	
Crystal size	$0.46 \times 0.72 \times 0.54$ mm ³	
Theta range for data collection	$2.66 - 27.49^\circ$	
Index ranges	$0 \leq h \leq 15, -13 \leq k \leq 0, -15 \leq l \leq 14$	
Reflections collected	3423	
Independent reflections	3275 [$R(\text{int}) = 0.0137$]	
Completeness to $\theta = 27.49^\circ$	99.7%	
Absorption correction	SHELXA	
Max. and min. transmission	0.9301 and 0.7485	
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares of F^2	
Data/restraints/parameters	3275/0/223	
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.109	
Final R indices [$I > 2$ sigma (I)]	$R1 = 0.0224, wR2 = 0.0574$	
R indices (all data)	$R1 = 0.0256, wR2 = 0.0587$	
Extinction coefficient	0.0080(6)	
Largest diff. peak and hole	0.318 and -0.429 e.Å ⁻³	

mononuclear complex. The nitrogen atom of the ligand, two terminal oxygen atoms and one oxygen atom from the water molecule are in the equatorial plane with the two oxygen atoms of the Schiff base occupying the opposite vertices of the distorted octahedron. The N(1)-C(7) [1.289(3) Å] and N(2)-C(8) [1.296(3) Å] bond distances in the complex are typical double bond [normal single bond is 1.364 Å]. *Cis*-bond angles ranges from 104.30(7) for O(12)-Mo-O(1) to 77.70(7) for N(1)-Mo-O(1W) and the range of *trans*-bond angle extends from 168.95(9) for

Fig. 1. View of molecular structure of the complex showing the atom-numbering scheme.

O(11)-Mo-O(1W) to 149.36(6) for O(1)-Mo-O(2). Incorporation of Mo into a five-member ring is, to a large extent, responsible for these distortions. The average Mo=O bond length 1.6962 Å and the O=Mo=O bond angle 104.20(10) are comparable to other such data reported for *cis*-MoO₂²⁺ group^{3,4}. The Mo-O(1W) [2.279 Å] is relatively long and the coordinated water is labile, a behavior due in part to the *trans*-effect⁵. The second water molecule is present as water of crystallization.

Table 2. Selected bond distances and angles for the complex

Distance (Å)		
Mo-O(11)	1.6902(18)	O(2)-C(8)
Mo-O(12)	1.7021(17)	N(1)-C(7)
Mo-O(1)	1.9291(15)	N(1)-N(2)
Mo-O(2)	2.0276(14)	N(2)-C(8)
Mo-N(1)	2.2399(17)	C(1)-C(7)
Mo-O(1W)	2.279(2)	C(8)-C(9)
O(1)-C(2)	1.356(2)	
Angle (°)		
O(11)-Mo-O(12)	104.20(10)	O(12)-Mo-O(1W)
O(11)-Mo-O(1)	99.45(8)	O(1)-Mo-O(1W)
O(12)-Mo-O(1)	104.30(7)	O(2)-Mo-O(1W)
O(11)-Mo-O(2)	95.79(8)	N(1)-Mo-O(1W)
O(12)-Mo-O(2)	97.43(7)	C(7)-N(1)-N(2)
O(1)-Mo-O(2)	149.36(6)	C(8)-N(2)-N(1)
O(11)-Mo-N(1)	91.69(8)	N(1)-C(7)-C(1)
O(12)-Mo-N(1)	161.90(8)	N(2)-C(8)-O(2)
O(1)-Mo-N(1)	81.11(6)	N(2)-C(8)-C(9)
O(2)-Mo-N(1)	71.99(6)	O(2)-C(8)-C(9)
O(11)-Mo-O(1W)	168.95(9)	

Infrared spectrum of the ligand (SAPH) shows bands at 1660vs, 1600s, 1510s and 1010ms cm⁻¹ tentatively assigned to amide I (ν_{C=O}), ν_{C=N}, amide II +ν_{C-O} (phenolic) and ν_{N-N}, respectively; and at 1570mw, 1480w, 1400m and

1050ms cm⁻¹ to different modes associated with pyrazine ring. In the complex, disappearance of ν_{C=O} band and appearance of a very strong band at ~1610 cm⁻¹ may be⁶ due to the >C=N-N=C< group resulting from coordination through deprotonated enolic oxygen; new bands at 1330–1340 cm⁻¹ assignable⁶ to ν_{NCO}⁻ support enolization. Positive shifts in the ν_{N-N} (Δν ~20–30 cm⁻¹) as well as ν_{C-O} (phenolic) bands (Δν ~30–40 cm⁻¹) relative to the free ligand values at 1010 and 1510 cm⁻¹, respectively, point⁶ to coordination through azomethine nitrogen and deprotonated phenolic oxygen in the complex. Strong bands characteristic of *cis*-MoO₂ are observed in the region 880–950 cm⁻¹ in agreement with literature reports^{1,7}. Dioxomolybdenum(vi) prefers to form the *cis*-MoO₂ structure for maximum utilization of the Mo_{dr}-O_{pr} orbitals for chemical bonding⁷ and the X-ray analysis has confirmed the presence of *cis*-MoO₂ moiety in the complex. Non-ligand bands at 555 and 530m cm⁻¹ may be assigned^{7,8} to ν_{Mo-N} and ν_{Mo-O} (phenolic), respectively.

Proton NMR signals due to OH (phenolic) and NH at δ 12.63 and 11.27 ppm of the Schiff base are absent in the complex supporting coordination through deprotonated phenolic and enolic oxygens. Downfield shift of the -CH-N- proton from the free ligand value (δ 9.29–9.56) in the complex confirms⁷, in line with crystallographic study, coordination through the azomethine nitrogen.

Electronic spectrum of the complex is characterized by a strong broad band at 23250 cm⁻¹ being shifted to 24300 cm⁻¹ in DMSO. High molar extinction value (ε = 3200 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) suggests that the band is charge transfer (LMCT) in origin⁷.

Isothermal heating (air oven, 115°) for 1 h results in total loss of water which suggests water is crystalline or at most weakly coordinated in the complex; weak coordination of a water molecule is apparent from X-ray study.

The molar conductivity (24.5 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) of the complex in DMSO indicates⁹ its non-electrolyte nature despite some solvolysis.

Experimental

All chemicals were obtained commercially and used without subsequent purification. The ligand (SAPH) and MoO₂Cl₂(DMF)₂ were prepared as described in literature^{9,10}. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1330 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (nujol) on a Hitachi 200-20 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a Bruker DPX-300 instrument. C, H, N were analyzed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 Series II apparatus. Molar conductivity was measured on a Systronics 306 conductivity meter.

Preparation of the complex : MoO₂Cl₂(DMF)₂ (100 mg, 0.289 mmol) was dissolved in methanol (10 cm³) containing SAPH (180 mg, 0.743 mmol) in hot methanol (20 cm³). The resulting yellow solution was refluxed for 2 h. On cooling the yellow precipitate that separated out was washed with hot methanol and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl₂. The complex was dissolved in DMSO containing few drops of water and the solution afforded yellow crystals suitable for crystallographic analysis in a week : yield 70% (Found : C, 36.19; N, 13.85; H, 3.12. C₁₂H₁₂N₄O₆Mo calcd. for : C, 35.64; N, 13.86; H, 2.97; H, 2.97%).

A selected single crystal with the approximate dimension (0.46 × 0.72 × 0.54 mm³) was glued to the ends of a thin glass fibre and transferred to a Siemens P4/S diffractometer using MoK_α (λ = 0.71073 Å) and a graphite monochromator. 3423 independent reflections were collected in the range 2.66° < θ < 27.49°, and 3275 independent reflections with I > 2σ(I) were used for further computation.

The title complex is monoclinic, space group P2(1)/n, mol. wt. 404.20, cell dimensions, a = 12.140(2), b = 10.3095(6), c = 12.2818(17) Å, V = 1431.5(3) Å³, Z = 4, D_{calc} = 1.875 mg/m³, F(000) = 808, R = 0.0224, R_w = 0.0574.

The structure was solved by direct methods using the SHELXTL package of computer programs¹¹. Neutral atom scattering factors were used with corrections for real and

imaginary anomalous dispersion¹². All structures were refined by full-matrix least-squares methods based on F² using SHELXTL-96¹³ and used all unique data. Non-hydrogen atoms were located in difference Fourier syntheses and refined isotropically.

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